

Munir's Permeable Digital Networking Model

Note: This model was designed for the Open University, UK, 2019. It has received accolades from global scholars at the PCF9 Conference, the Commonwealth of Learning, 2019

Catalyst: Digital Literacy, Ownership, Conscious Networking

The journey of an individual's online learning starts as a visitor, at which point they are considered mere users of the web. Initially, they keep interactions anonymous and activities invisible due to privacy concerns. They are not opposed to using online platforms but are cautious about their digital identity. However, some individuals may be unaware of the realities of online learning and may end up diving into a pool of delusion without exercising due diligence. They may view all online resources as authentic sources of learning and consider people they meet online as their digital relatives.

Over time, individuals who are mindful of their online presence begin to participate in organized open and closed groups for social and academic ties. As individuals become more engaged in virtual communities, their participation broadens in groups that share common interests and attributes. This gradual expansion of involvement can shift them to become digital residents. Spending most of their time in these digital spaces, they feel comfortable building academic and social relationships. However, they may lack consciousness and exposure to authentic sources of learning and instead prefer to exist within a self-contained bubble that could be detrimental to their well-being.

Finally, collectives are formed to organize, filter, discover, evaluate, and recommend things to learn, for example, from online repositories.

Dron and Anderson (2014) proposed the heuristic of social forms, but its lack of clarity hinders the creation of a community of practice. To achieve this, we must focus on avoiding absolute boundaries between communities. Digital literacy, ownership, and conscious networking act as catalysts for digital networking. Innovative, affordable/low-cost, and accessible technology can bridge the knowledge gap, promote gender equity and inclusivity, ensure digital learning sustainability, and improve skills, but it's important to consider the sociocultural context and choose culturally appropriate tools and platforms to sustain digital learning practices.

Note: This model must be used in combination with **Munir's Digital Taxonomy of Learning**

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